

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Mousa****FIRST NAME: Ahmed****PROGRAM CODE : DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Professor Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used Zotero to insert some references

The author used the following software: MS. Word

The author did use Grammarly

COURSEPACK PERIOD SIX (6)

QUIZ: A SUMMARY OF ASSESSMENT

1. **In the field of essay writing, it is important for the researcher to follow the basics to ensure a well-written essay that will engage the participants and readers, as a result, it is essential to have a well-structured beginning for the essay. In this context, the researcher must follow the following basic steps for good start.**

- Clearly define the research questions and hypothesis, and develop the list of references.
- Provide a plan for the data collection process, discuss the required sample, and define the research questions.
- The researcher should start the work early, clearly define the question and analyze the task, and construct an initial plan.¹**
- Discuss the literature review, construct an initial plan, define the question, and analyze the task.

¹ EUCLID, ACA-401 Coursepack. Period 1 (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

2. **The literature review chapter is very critical to establish the available studies and data, what is known in the literature review and the gap analysis. It is expected that the researcher will spend a long time in the literature review process. There are numerous critical reminders to follow in order to construct a well-written literature review chapter**
- Appropriate use of numbers, acronyms, references, and citations.
 - Appropriate use of questions, citations, spelling, and avoiding plagiarism.
 - Appropriate use of commas, punctuations, use of parallel construction, and active voice.²**
 - Appropriate use of translation, numbers, singular and plural, and tables.
3. **What are the proper questions that researchers should ask in the beginning, using the Turabian manual for writing?**
- What should my conclusion include? What is my data collection process? What is the required sampling?
 - Will I use interviews or surveys to collect the data? What is my inclusion and exclusion criteria?
 - Should I prepare the references first? Do I have enough literature review?
 - What should we think? What should we do? What must we understand before we know what to do?³**
4. **The Turabian manual provided critical “style” that the researcher should follow; the provided instructions include.**

² EUCLID, 17.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15.

- Appendix, revising the draft, instructor feedback, and engaging sources.
- Bibliography, citations, references, interviews, and surveys.
- Spelling, language, translation, first draft, writing plan, and electronic citations.
- Spelling, punctuation, names, quotations, tables, numbers, and abbreviations.**⁴

5. **What should researchers target when drafting their report?**

- Ensuring the references and citations are according to the appropriate writing style.
- Proofreading the document and ensuring the research questions are carefully listed.
- Providing all the evidences, citations, and strong conclusion.
- Construct a comfortable report, develop appropriate drafting habits, appropriate use of footnotes and quotations, and avoid plagiarism.**⁵

6. **What are the best practices when revising the draft according to the Turabian style of writing?**

- Ensuring the appropriate punctuation, spelling, and grammar.
- Ensuring that all the arguments' blind spots have been verified, checking the introduction, body, and conclusion section.**⁶
- Ensure the proper use of tables, graphs, and figures.
- A strong introduction and a decisive conclusion.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, 162.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, 48.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 68.

7. **The Qualitative Dissertation book provided useful instructions for the researcher to organize and manage the project.**
- Print all surveys and interview transcripts, and references.
 - Create a list of all drafts, reviewers, and revision details.
 - Keep a list of all figures, tables, equations, and references.
 - Create a “workspace”, getting familiar with the computer, keep various dissertation drafts, and keep physical evidence.⁷**
8. **The Qualitative Dissertation book discussed the importance of integrity and avoiding plagiarism. The types of plagiarism included.**
- Paraphrasing others’ work and citing the main source without following appropriate writing style format.
 - Use the exact words from other authors after attaining approval; however, failing to cite properly.
 - Using text from available journals, published reports, and dissertations without the need to cite them, and only cite exact words.
 - Using other author’s words without proper citation, falsifying data, and using others’ ideas without proper citation.⁸**
9. **For the fifth period, assignment 5B, the researcher was asked to analyze two dissertations and evaluate the following:**

⁷ Bloomberg Linda Dale and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, 1 edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Inc., 2008), 3

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 24

- Quality of the literature review and the introduction.
- Use of the figures, tables and references.
- Punctuation and citation.
- Overall dissertation quality, abstract and structure quality, and proper use of the English language, and quality of recommendations and conclusions.⁹**

10. **The “Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study” video provided by Dr. Adu indicated that the methodology chapter should include the following.**

- Selection criteria, literature review, sampling procedure, data analysis, and conclusion.
- Research questions, data analysis, literature review, IRB process, establishing a timeline.
- Introduction, statistical analysis, literature review, data procedures, and conclusion.
- Study purpose, introduction, overview of the required information and methodology, demographics data, and data analysis.¹⁰**

⁹ EUCLID, ACA-401 Coursepack. Period 5 (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019).

¹⁰ Adu, Philip. 2016. Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study by Philip Adu, Ph.D. YouTube. March 06, 2016. 01:05:16. <https://youtu.be/KRHvxY3N708>.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.